

Reporting Quality of Non-inferiority and Equivalence Rheumatoid Arthritis Randomized Clinical Trials: Protocol for a Systematic Review

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- **Administrative Information:**

- Registration:

- We submitted our study protocol details to the international Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) on May 2, 2024. We are waiting for their reply to confirm our registration.
- This study protocol details will also be registered in Open Science Framework (OSF), and this protocol document will be uploaded there May 4, 2024.

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- Support

- No financial support was received for developing the protocol or the systematic review.

- **Introduction**

The design of clinical trials can be classified according to hypothesis testing into three main types: superiority, non-inferiority (NI), and equivalence (EQ) trials. Superiority trials are the most common, and the aim is to establish whether a new intervention is more effective than a placebo or the standard of care. In NI trials, the aim is to establish whether the new intervention is at least not clinically significant worse than the established treatment. In EQ trials, the aim is to establish whether the new intervention is clinically similar to established treatment(1). In the last decade, the field of rheumatology, specifically the subfield of rheumatoid arthritis (RA), has witnessed a significant increase in the number of NI and EQ trials(2). One explanation for this fact is that the availability of more effective RA treatments makes it more difficult to demonstrate the superiority of newer interventions. Furthermore, it is unethical to test a new treatment against a placebo in the presence of an established effective standard of care(3). The biosimilar industry is expanding given the loss of patent protection of many

biologics (4). Regulatory agencies are still asking for proving non-inferiority or equivalence to the reference biologic via NI/EQ trials as a final step in the approval process for biosimilars(5-7). Finally, given the evolving nature of newer, cheaper alternative strategy interventions, NI trials are the most suitable for demonstrating their efficacy to substitute older and more-expensive options (2).

However, the design, implementation, and interpretation of NI/EQ trials requires particular attention. There is always the risk of mis-interpreting the results or falsely claiming non-inferiority or equivalence (8, 9). The Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) 2010 statement is a guideline released by a group of researchers aiming to ensure transparent, clear, and complete reporting of clinical trials (10). High-quality reporting is important for informing decisions in clinical practice. There is a special extension of this statement for NI/EQ trials that was last updated in 2012 (11). Previous studies have suggested poor adherence to reporting guidelines (10, 11). The primary aim of this study is to conduct a systematic review to assess the quality of reporting of NI/EQ trials in RA in the last 10 years based on the last updated extension of the CONSORT for NI/EQ trials. To our knowledge, this review would be the first systematic investigation of the quality of NI/EQ trials in RA.

- **Research Questions and Objectives:**

- The main aim of this systematic review is to answer the following questions:

- What has been the quality of the reporting of NI/EQ clinical trials in RA over the last 10 years?
- Has there been a difference in reporting quality between 2014–2018 and 2019–2024?

- Primary objectives:

- To conduct a systematic review to evaluate the quality of reporting of NI/EQ clinical trials in RA over the last 10 years.
- To compare the quality of reporting of these trials between 2014–2018 and 2019–2024.

- Secondary objectives:
 - To compare the quality of reporting of biosimilars NI/EQ trials to other NI/EQ trials in RA.
 - To compare the quality of reporting between industry- and non-industry-funded NI/EQ trials in RA.

Methods

- **Eligibility Criteria**

- Inclusion criteria
 - Published reports of NI or EQ randomized controlled trials (RCTs) in RA only with an NI or EQ hypothesis involving the primary outcome in the primary analysis.
- Exclusion criteria
 - Early-phase (i.e., Phase I or II) trials
 - Pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic studies
 - Trial extensions after primary outcome data analysis
 - Reports of secondary analysis
 - Nonrandomized studies
 - Unpublished trials
 - Conference abstracts without published full article.
 - Studies with NI/EQ hypothesis involving only the secondary outcomes.
- Note:
 - NI/EQ RCTs would be identified from the title, hypothesis, objectives, study design section, or the primary analysis plan.
 - In the case of multiple reports for one study, only the report that has the primary analysis that involves the primary outcome is included (if needed, we refer to the trial protocol in the trial registry)
 - The RCTs in transition phase between II-III, were excluded.
 - Studies with population including mixed RA and other diseases were not included.
 - When the study has two co-primary outcomes for clinical and pharmacokinetics/pharmacodynamics outcomes, the focus would be on the assessment of the quality of reporting the primary clinical endpoint.

- **Information Sources**

- We will conduct our search in the following three databases:
 - Embase on Ovid interface
 - Medline on Ovid interface
 - Cochrane Library
- The aim of this review is to assess the reporting qualities of published articles, and thus we will not search for unpublished works.

- **Search Strategy**

- Keywords that will be used in the search strategy are RA, non-inferiority, and equivalence trials. We will combine both keywords with subject headings in the search for more comprehensive results. For Embase and Medline databases, we will use tested RCT filters from InterTASC Information Specialists' Sub-Group (ISSG)(12). For more comprehensive results we will combine both the RCT limits provided in the databases (Embase/Ovid and Medline/Ovid) with the RCT filters by OR.
- We will limit our search by publication date from 01/01/2014 till the date of search (expected in May 4, 2024). This will correspond to the last 10 years. We selected this limit because the last updated extension of the CONSORT statement for NI/EQ trials was published in December 2012. This offers researchers and journals approximately one year to be familiarized with the latest guidelines. We will use items from the CONSORT checklist for NI/EQ to assess the reporting quality.
- The drafts of search strategies for the three databases are available in Appendix A.

- **Study Records**

- Data management

- Search results from all three databases will be imported in Covidence web-based program to aid in screening of records, full text review, and data extraction.
 - Duplicate records will be removed automatically by Covidence. The remaining duplicates will be removed manually during the screening process.

- Selection process

- Two independent reviewers (OA, MH) will screen the records at each stage of the study selection process (abstract screening and full text review). Conflicts will be resolved by discussion between the two reviewers.

- Data collection process

- Data forms will be entered into Covidence to facilitate data extraction. Data collection will be done by one reviewer (OA) and will be verified by another reviewer (MH). Conflict will be resolved by discussion between the two reviewers.

- **Data items**

- Data that will be collected from the studies will include study characteristics and quality data.

- Study characteristics:

- Study characteristics will include basic information: first author, journal name, publication year, funding source (industry vs non-industry funded), sample size, number of trial arms and type of study design (NI vs EQ)
 - We will also determine if the trial will compare a biosimilar to its reference biologic medication or not.
 - We will also record the author's conclusion.

- Quality data

- Quality data form was made from the essential parts of the checklist items from extension of the CONSORT statement for NI/EQ trials similar to the way that was used in a previous systematic review assessing reporting quality of NI RCTs that compare antiretroviral therapies by Lo et al. 2023 with some modifications (11, 13). We used similar items used in that review to facilitate comparison.
 - Quality data include whether the RCT is identified as NI/EQ in the title, rationale of NI/EQ design, whether the NI/EQ margin is pre-specified and justified, whether the sample size was calculated using a NI/EQ criterion, whether there is specification if

1- or 2-sided confidence interval approach was used, type of analysis used (intention to treat (ITT), per protocol analysis (PP), or both) and whether there was a figure illustrating point estimate, CI, and NI/EQ margin.

- Misleading interpretations will be defined by one of the following: conclusion of NI/EQ despite the CI crossing the NI/EQ margins, conclusion of NI/EQ despite incongruent analyses (e.g., the ITT analysis showed NI while the PP analysis did not) or using ambiguous wording in the interpretation.
 - Superiority might be withdrawn from the outcome for which NI/EQ was hypothesized, but this can be justified based on extension of the CONSORT statement for NI/EQ trials (11) if all the following were met: testing for superiority was pre-specified, two-sided CI for the summary statistic that compare that the two interventions are entirely toward the favourable side, not including the null effect, and ITT analysis were used.
- A draft of the data form is available in Appendix B

- **Data Analysis and Presentation of the Results**

- Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis (PRISMA) flow diagram will be used to illustrate the review process.
- Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize results of study characteristics and overall quality data.
- Chi-squared test will be used to assess difference of quality data between groups: 2014-2018 vs. 2019-2024 periods, biosimilar trials vs. other trials, and industry- vs. non-industry-funded trials.
- The results will be presented by both narrative form and tabulation and graphs for further illustrations.
- Statistical analysis will be done by SPSS.
- In this type of systematic review, there is no need for assessing the quality of the included studies given that we are not concerned with the results of the trials or doing statistical synthesis. We are concerned about assessing the quality of reporting.

- **References**

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Appendix A: Search Strategies

- **EMBASE/Ovid**

1. exp randomized controlled trial/
2. Controlled clinical trial/
3. random\$.ti,ab.
4. randomization/
5. intermethod comparison/
6. placebo.ti,ab.
7. (compare or compared or comparison).ti.
8. ((evaluated or evaluate or evaluating or assessed or assess) and (compare or compared or comparing or comparison)).ab.
9. (open adj label).ti,ab.
10. ((double or single or doubly or singly) adj (blind or blinded or blindly)).ti,ab.
11. double blind procedure/
12. parallel group\$1.ti,ab.
13. (crossover or cross over).ti,ab.
14. ((assign\$ or match or matched or allocation) adj5 (alternate or group\$1 or intervention\$1 or patient\$1 or subject\$1 or participant\$1)).ti,ab.
15. (assigned or allocated).ti,ab.
16. (controlled adj7 (study or design or trial)).ti,ab.
17. (volunteer or volunteers).ti,ab.
18. human experiment/
19. trial.ti.
20. or/1-19
21. (random\$ adj sampl\$ adj7 ("cross section\$" or questionnaire\$1 or survey\$ or database\$1)).ti,ab. not (comparative study/ or controlled study/ or randomi?ed controlled.ti,ab. or randomly assigned.ti,ab.)
22. Cross-sectional study/ not (exp randomized controlled trial/ or controlled clinical study/ or controlled study/ or randomi?ed controlled.ti,ab. or control group\$1.ti,ab.)
23. (((case adj control\$) and random\$) not randomi?ed controlled).ti,ab.
24. Systematic review.ti,ab. not (trial or study).ti.
25. (nonrandom\$ not random\$).ti,ab.
26. "random field\$".ti,ab.
27. (random cluster adj3 sampl\$).ti,ab.
28. (review.ab. and review.pt.) not trial.ti.
29. "we searched".ab. and (review.ti. or review.pt.)
30. "update review".ab.
31. (databases adj4 searched).ab.
32. (rat or rats or mouse or mice or swine or porcine or murine or sheep or lambs or pigs or piglets or rabbit or rabbits or cat or cats or dog or dogs or cattle or bovine or monkey or monkeys or trout or marmoset\$1).ti. and animal experiment/
33. Animal experiment/ not (human experiment/ or human/)
34. or/21-33
35. 20 not 34

36. exp rheumatoid arthritis/
37. (Rheumatoid or RA).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
38. exp non-inferiority trial/
39. (Noninferiority or noninferior or noninferior* or Non-inferior or non-inferiority or non-inferior* or Inferiority or inferior or inferior*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
40. exp equivalence trial/ or exp "equivalence trial (topic)"/
41. (Equivalence or equivalent or equivalency or equivalen* or Non-equivalence or non-equivalent or non-equivalency or non-equivalen* or Nonequivalence or nonequivalent or nonequivalency or nonequivalen*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, drug trade name, original title, device manufacturer, drug manufacturer, device trade name, keyword heading word, floating subheading word, candidate term word]
42. 36 or 37
43. 38 or 39 or 40 or 41
44. 42 and 43
45. 44 and 35
46. limit 44 to (clinical trial or randomized controlled trial or controlled clinical trial or multicenter study or phase 3 clinical trial or phase 4 clinical trial)
47. 45 or 46
48. limit 47 to yr="2014 -Current"

- **Note:** numbers from 1-35 correspond to RCT filter, source:
 - (ISSG) IISS-G. Randomized Controlled Trials and Other Trials: Filters [cited 2024 4th April]. Available from: <https://sites.google.com/a/york.ac.uk/issg-search-filters-resource/home/rcts>.

- **Medline/Ovid**

1. exp randomized controlled trial/
2. controlled clinical trial.pt.
3. randomized.ab.
4. placebo.ab.
5. clinical trials as topic/
6. randomly.ab.
7. trial.ti.
8. or/1-7
9. exp animals/ not humans/
10. 8 not 9
11. exp Arthritis, Rheumatoid/
12. (Rheumatoid or RA).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]

13. (Noninferiority or noninferior or noninferior* or Non-inferior or non-inferiority or non-inferior* or Inferiority or inferior or inferior*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]
14. exp Equivalence Trials as Topic/ or exp Equivalence Trial/
15. (Equivalence or equivalent or equivalency or equivalen* or Non-equivalence or non-equivalent or non-equivalency or non-equivalen* or Nonequivalence or nonequivalent or nonequivalency or nonequivalen*).mp. [mp=title, book title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms, population supplementary concept word, anatomy supplementary concept word]
16. 11 or 12
17. 13 or 14 or 15
18. 16 and 17
19. 18 and 10
20. limit 18 to (adaptive clinical trial or clinical trial, all or clinical trial, phase iii or clinical trial, phase iv or clinical trial or controlled clinical trial or equivalence trial or multicenter study or pragmatic clinical trial or randomized controlled trial)
21. 19 or 20
22. limit 21 to yr="2014 -Current"

- **Note:** numbers from 1-10 correspond to RCT filter, source:
 - (ISSG) IISS-G. Randomized Controlled Trials and Other Trials: Filters [cited 2024 4th April]. Available from: <https://sites.google.com/a/york.ac.uk/issg-search-filters-resource/home/rcts>.

- **Cochrane Library**

- #1 MeSH descriptor: [Arthritis, Rheumatoid] explode all trees
- #2 (Rheumatoid OR RA):ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)
- #3 (Noninferiority OR noninferior OR noninferior* OR Non-inferior OR non-inferiority OR non-inferior* OR Inferiority OR inferior OR inferior*):ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)
- #4 MeSH descriptor: [Equivalence Trial] explode all trees
- #5 MeSH descriptor: [Equivalence Trials as Topic] explode all trees
- #6 (Equivalence OR equivalent OR equivalency OR equivalen* OR Non-equivalence OR non-equivalent OR non-equivalency OR non-equivalen* OR Nonequivalence OR nonequivalent OR nonequivalency OR nonequivalen*):ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)
- #7 #1 OR #2
- #8 #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6
- #9 #7 AND #8 with Publication Year from 2014 to 2024, in Trials

Appendix B: Data Form

Study Characteristics

- **Q1: First author**
- **Q2: Journal name**
- **Publication time**
 - **Q3: Publication year**
 - **Q4: Publication period**
 - 2014-2018
 - 2019-2024
- **Q5: Funding source**
 - Industry-funded
 - Non-industry-funded
 - Mixed
 - Not specified
- **Q6: Sample size**
- **Q7: Number of arms of the trial**
- **Q8: Type of the design (Based on primary outcome analysis)**
 - NI
 - EQ
 - Mixed (NI+EQ)
 - Mixed (NI+Superiority)
 - Mixed (EQ+Superiority)
 - Mixed (NI+EQ+Superiority)
 - Others
- **Q9: Type of tested intervention**
 - Medicinal product
 - Strategy
 - Others
- **Q10: If the trial involves medicinal product, is it biosimilar related (trials comparing biosimilar to the reference biologic)?**
 - Yes
 - No
- **Q11: If the trial involves medicinal product, is it comparing different dosing, frequency of administration or mode of administration of the same medication?**
 - Yes
 - No

- **Q12: Authors' conclusion**
 - NI shown
 - NI rejected
 - EQ shown
 - EQ rejected
 - Superiority shown
 - Inferiority shown
 - Nonequivalence shown
 - Inconclusive
 - Others

- **Q13: RCT results, according to the author conclusion**
 - Positive
 - Negative

Quality Reporting

- **Q14: Trial identified as NI/EQ in the title?**
 - Yes
 - No
- **Q15: Rationale for NI/EQ design stated?**
 - Yes
 - No
- **Q16: NIM/EQM specified?** (NIM = non-inferiority margin, EQM = Equivalence margin)
 - Yes
 - No
- **Q17: NIM/EQM justified?**
 - Yes
 - No
- **Q18: The sample size was calculated using a NI/EQ criterion?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - Not enough information on sample size calculation given.
- **Q19: Specify whether a 1- or 2-sided confidence interval approach was used?**
 - Yes
 - No
- **Q20: Analysis used:** (mITT = modified ITT, (m)ITT = ITT or mITT)
 - ITT only
 - mITT only
 - ITT and mITT only
 - PP only
 - (m)ITT and PP
 - Not stated
- **Q21: Figure illustrating point estimate, CI, and NIM/EQM?**
 - Yes
 - No

- Interpretation
 - **Q22: Misleading interpretation?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - Not enough information to judge
 - **Q23: If yes to previous question, choose one of the following:**
 - Conclusion of NI/EQ despite the CI crossing the NI/EQ margins.
 - Study is concluding NI/EQ despite Incongruent analyses (i.e., the ITT analysis showed NI and the PP analysis did not)
 - Using ambiguous wording in their interpretation
 - Others

- Superiority conclusion
 - **Q24: Is a superiority conclusion drawn for outcome(s) for which NI/EQ was hypothesized?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - **Q25: If yes to Q24, to the previous question, answer the following questions:**
 - **Q25a: Is the 2-sided CI for the summary statistic that compare the 2 interventions entirely to the right of the null effect (or toward the favourable side and not including the null effect)?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - Not mentioned
 - **Q25b: Was the testing for superiority prespecified?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - **Q25c: Was the analysis (m)ITT?**
 - Yes
 - No
 - Not mentioned
 - **Q26: if yes to Q24, was superiority conclusion justified (by answering yes to all of three previous questions: Q26a-c)?**
 - Yes
 - No